

TEACHING AND LEARNING ENGLISH AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE: TESOL PRINCIPLES

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Abstract Teaching and learning foreign languages are becoming one of the top priorities of developing countries. To conclude, as English language is becoming one of the top languages with the most speakers, countries are trying to implement it as a main subject at educational establishments. A look back over time shows that language teaching and learning have often moved between these two orientations and that in many cases teachers and learners alike have tried to strike a balance between the two poles. This conflict of interests was evident in the past centuries of the European history of language learning, teaching and (University) education and also applies to the 200-year-history of teaching/learning English in Germany since 1800. This is how long it took, in fact, until English was established as the main foreign language in society and education in Germany¹. In this article, I am going to investigate FLT (foreign language teaching) principles, and ways of acquiring L2 successfully by comparing and contrasting other scholars' works done on linguistics and methodology.

Key words: priority, strike, education, FLT, L2, methodology.

Introduction

The 18th century marked the beginning of a meteoric rise of the popularity of the English language. In the first two thirds of the 18th century, English was only sporadically present in schools and universities across the German countries. However, an interest in the language was continuously fed at this stage by the

¹ cf. Doff/Klippel 2007, 17 ff.

growing desire to read: formative works on politics, science, philosophy, theology, art and English literature attracted a large number of educated adult readers. In many cases, these works had to be read in the original due to a lack of translation.

Therefore, reading in

English was a central skill that had to be acquired individually, through home or school study. This is reflected in a number of textbooks from this period, which typically included a grammar part and additional discussions/dialogues, a dictionary, lists of key words or short reading texts.

The set-up of the grammar parts of most textbooks for English was based on Latin grammar books. The rules and illustrations with example sentences, which often came from well-known literary works, were presented in German.

English as a school subject in the 19th century: The number of selftaught adult learners of English continued to rise in the 19th century. One of the most important new phenomena was that in this century English teaching was established in boys' (and later on in girls') state secondary schools as a school subject². This change demanded a differentiation and adaptation of content, material and methods to address the young target group adequately. Although the overall goal of teaching English was language proficiency, slightly different objectives were pursued in the different types of schools for boys and girls. There also was a growing competition between the emerging ›real‹ institutions (Realanstalten) in the 19th century and the traditional grammar schools (Gymnasien). The former put a focus on natural sciences and the practice of modern foreign languages (i. e. as part of a marketplace tradition). The latter focused on classical languages associated with a humanistic and formal education concept (rather in line with a monastery tradition).

The most ›modern‹ foreign language teaching at this stage probably took place at secondary schools for girls, where principles that are known today as ›communicative foreign language teaching‹ and ›English as a working language‹, i. e. the use of English for communicative purposes in subjects other than languages

² cf. Klippel 1994; Doff 2002

were realised (cf. Doff 2002). The different approaches led to controversial discussions about goals and methods of English language teaching as illustrated in the following quotation:

I do not greatly value hearing a man speak perfect English, any skilled waiter can do that, babbling in institutional French is not worth much because they do not actually know why after this or that conjunction a subjunctive comes if they know the existing rule. [...] Let girls chat about the weather and walks, the educated have something else to do. [...] He should penetrate the genius of languages, he should study the idea of nations, the ideas of foreigners, not master their words, he should have to study the historical background of languages and the type of languages, this method should and must come from the grammar school. The educated person from the grammar school, the only and real nursery of the educated, must be opposed to this crude language study [...].³

Even if the demands of the reformers did not completely dominate in the 20th century, this movement greatly influenced the academic debate in foreign language learning and teaching across Europe in the decades and century to follow. The first third of the 20th century was dominated by the question of which role the knowledge and understanding of cultural aspects should play in the teaching of foreign languages.

6 Principles of TESOL

Teaching English to Speakers of Other Languages is called TESOL. Although it is most frequently used to refer to language instruction that takes place in English-speaking nations, it can be used to teach English to non-native English speakers either abroad or in English-speaking nations.

TESOL has its own principles:

PRINCIPLE 1. KNOW YOUR LEARNERS: Teachers learn basic information about their students' families, languages, cultures, and educational backgrounds to engage them in class and prepare and deliver lessons more effectively.

³ von Reinhardtstöttner 1868, 13 f., translation SD

Some Practices for Principle 1 Teachers gain information about their learners.

Teachers collect information about their students' linguistic and educational backgrounds to determine correct placement for students. They also seek to learn a new student's cultural and geographic background as a resource for classroom learning.

Teachers embrace and leverage the resources that learners bring to the classroom to enhance learning. Teachers tap their learners' prior knowledge purposefully in their teaching. They try to determine what gifts and talents students bring to the classroom, what interests motivate them, what life experiences they have had that are curriculum-related, and what else in their backgrounds has influenced their personalities and beliefs.

PRINCIPLE 2. CREATE CONDITIONS FOR LANGUAGE LEARNING.

Teachers create a classroom culture so students feel comfortable. They make decisions regarding the physical environment, the materials, and the social integration of students to promote language learning.

Some Practices for Principle 2. **Teachers demonstrate expectations of success for all learners.** Student achievement is affected by teacher expectations of success. Teachers must hold high expectations and communicate them clearly to all their students—English learners and other classmates, which will motivate them to perform at a high level.

Teachers plan instruction to enhance and support students' motivation for language learning. Language learning is difficult and takes a very long time. Learners may not see the benefits of spending time and energy in learning English if the effort does not have an early payoff or it feels outside their own comfort zone. However, we know that motivation is an important condition for language learning, so teachers need to engage their learners and motivate them to work persistently at learning the new language.

PRINCIPLE 3. DESIGN HIGH-QUALITY LESSONS FOR LANGUAGE DEVELOPMENT

Teachers plan meaningful lessons that promote language learning and help students develop learning strategies and critical thinking skills. These lessons evolve from the learning objectives.

Some Practices for Principle 3

Teachers use comprehensible input to convey information to students. Comprehensible input is of primary importance for progress in the target language. Whether oral or written, comprehensible input helps English learners understand the meaning of the communication. Teachers scaffold the language input in multiple ways to aid learner perception and promote understanding.

Teachers communicate clear instructions to carry out the learning task.

Teachers use and teach consistent classroom management practices and routines throughout the school year in an effort to help students understand what is expected of them in a classroom and throughout a lesson. Teachers use simple directions with patterned language that they repeat each time.

PRINCIPLE 4 ADAPT LESSON DELIVERY AS NEEDED

Teachers continually assess as they teach—observing and reflecting on learners’ responses to determine whether the students are reaching the learning objectives. If students struggle or are not challenged enough, teachers consider the possible reasons and adjust their lessons.

Some Practices for Principle 4

Teachers check student comprehension frequently and adjust instruction according to learner responses. To teach effectively, teachers need to evaluate what students know and what they do not know, in real time. We do not want to wait until the end of a lesson or the end of a unit to discover that our students have misunderstood a key concept or have incorrectly learned critical vocabulary.

Classroom Example: Teachers check comprehension with group response techniques.

Teachers can use quick comprehension checks during a lesson to gauge how the class is doing. Some group response activities include

- Thumbs Up/Thumbs Down
- Response Boards (all students respond individually on a dry-erase board or sheet of paper and show the teacher)
- 3-2-1 for Self-Assessment, and

PRINCIPLE 5. MONITOR AND ASSESS STUDENT LANGUAGE DEVELOPMENT

Language learners learn at different rates, so teachers regularly monitor and assess their language development in order to advance their learning efficiently. Teachers also gather data to measure student language growth.

Some Practices for Principle 5

Teachers monitor student errors.

By interacting frequently with our students, we can acquire a great deal of information about their progress. Some teachers record the results of their interactions (e.g., correct and incorrect uses of English) in an anecdotal way, use a check list, or change student grouping patterns and/or partners, depending on their newly developing proficiency.

Classroom Example: Teachers reteach when errors indicate that students misunderstood or learned the material incorrectly.

When errors are not part of the language development process, teachers plan for reteaching or additional practice. They may present a mini-lesson on the topic for the whole class or work with a small group of learners who need the support.

Teachers provide ongoing effective feedback strategically.

To be constructive, a teacher’s feedback in response to a learner’s error is delivered strategically and in a timely manner but it must also suit the age and language development level of the student. The feedback can be positive or corrective. It is important that the feedback be specific and related to what learners are doing well in addition to what they can improve.

Classroom Example: Teachers deliver feedback in a timely manner.

Students may be more able to use feedback if it is not delayed. Timeliness is more important with oral feedback than with written feedback. Private feedback is appreciated by all students, no matter their age.

PRINCIPLE 6. ENGAGE AND COLLABORATE WITHIN A COMMUNITY OF PRACTICE

Teachers collaborate with others in the profession to provide the best support for their learners with respect to programming, instruction, and advocacy. They also continue their own professional learning.

Teachers collaborate with one another.

Exemplary teachers collaborate with others in the profession to provide the best possible support for their learners. They meet with colleagues to co-plan and share their expertise about second language acquisition as well as instructional techniques appropriate for students at different levels of proficiency.

Example: Teachers meet with colleagues regularly to co-plan for future learning.

ESL/ELD teachers need to become co-planners to ensure their students' success in developing English language and content proficiency. These planning opportunities permit ESL/ELD teachers to become aware of the extent of the content learning required for students. They also allow ESL/ELD teachers to share information about students' language proficiency with content teachers. The school administrators can help by making certain that scheduling allows teachers to collaborate with colleagues for planning.

Teachers are fully engaged in their profession.

Teachers participate in continuous learning and ongoing professional development and they also reflect critically on their own classroom practices. They develop leadership skills so they can be a resource in their school and get involved in designing programs and developing curricula.

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